

Thermodynamic Theories of Precipitation, Dissolution, Freezing and Melting Potentials†

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THE precipitation and dissolution potentials are a novel class of phenomena which have been extensively studied during recent years¹⁻⁷. Thermodynamic theories of precipitation and dissolution potentials have also been developed^{8,9}. The purpose of the present paper is to develop an improved model and the corresponding theory of this phenomena. It is also intended to examine to what extent the new theory agrees with new data on precipitation potential using micro electrode¹⁰ and dissolution potential using rotating electrode⁵, and to develop corresponding theories of freezing potential¹¹⁻¹⁵ and melting potential¹⁶ in order to explain the experimental results.

The model used earlier is based on the postulate that precipitation potentials essentially arise due to a difference in the rate of attachment of cations and anions during crystallisation or to a difference in detachment rate during dissolution in addition to other factors. In this model, the crucial site is supposed to be crystal(α)-solution(β) interface. On the solution side of the interface, ions are supposed to exist as bare ions. So long as the crystallisation or dissolution proceeds, both the regions are in non-equilibrium. However, when the crystal of an electrolyte is in contact with its saturated solution for a long time, equilibrium is established. The free energy change in the electrical process is equivalent to the free energy change during transfer of bare ions from the β -phase to α -phase.

The precipitation potential⁸ has been conceptually defined as follows. 'The precipitation potential difference arising from an electrical double layer developed at a liquid-crystal interface by the ion migration from the liquid phase. The algebraic sign of the precipitation potential is the same as the electrostatic polarity (+) or (-), of the end of the dipolar double layer on the crystal side of the interface'. Similarly, the conceptual definition⁸ of dissolution potential is as follows. 'The dissolution potentials is the potential difference arising from an electrical double layer developed at a liquid crystal interface by the process of crystal dissolution (ion migration) into the liquid phase. The algebraic sign of the dissolution potential is the same as the electrostatic polarity (+) or (-), of the end of the dipolar double layer on the crystal side of the interface'.

When precipitation takes place, the bare ions from the interface after being stripped of hydrated water molecules get attached in the lattice. The stripping occurs in the adjacent liquid phase just before entering the crystal lattice. The essential reaction occurring at the interface is

Similarly, when dissolution takes place, the bare ions detach from the lattice and plunge into the medium and the basic reaction occurring at the interface is

Phase potential and diffusion potential or similar potential are usually superimposed in the potentials observed during dissolution and precipitation of electrolytes by the techniques described earlier. The double layer in both the cases consist of bare cation and anion.

Precipitation potential: Based on the above considerations, Rastogi and Khan obtained the following expression for the precipitation potential⁸ for uni-univalent electrolyte,

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = t_1^\alpha[\mu_1^{0\alpha} + RT \ln a_1^\alpha - \mu_1^{0\beta} - RT \ln a_1^\beta] - t_2^\alpha[\mu_2^{0\alpha} + RT \ln a_2^\alpha - \mu_2^{0\beta} - RT \ln a_2^\beta] \quad (1)$$

where, F = Faraday and $(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta}$ = potential between α - and β -phase. Further,

$$t_1^\alpha = \frac{U_1^\alpha}{U_1^\alpha + U_2^\alpha}; t_2^\alpha = \frac{U_2^\alpha}{U_1^\alpha + U_2^\alpha} \quad (2)$$

where, U_1^α and U_2^α are the speeds of attachment of cations and anions. $\mu_i^{0\alpha}$ and $\mu_i^{0\beta}$ are the standard chemical potential of the ion i in α - and β -phase, respectively.

Equation (1) can be written as

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = t_1^\alpha[(\mu_1^{0\alpha} - \mu_1^{0\beta})] - t_2^\alpha[(\mu_2^{0\alpha} - \mu_2^{0\beta})] + [(t_1^\alpha - t_2^\alpha) RT \ln \frac{a_1^\alpha}{a_2^\alpha}] \quad (3)$$

when it is assumed that

$$\frac{a_1^\alpha}{a_1^\beta} = \frac{a_2^\alpha}{a_2^\beta} = \frac{a^\alpha}{a^\beta}$$

† Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

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Equation (3) can be rearranged as

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = t_1^\alpha [\mu_1^{\alpha\beta} - \mu_1^{\alpha\alpha} - RT \ln a_1^{\alpha\beta}] - t_2^\alpha [\mu_2^{\alpha\beta} - \mu_2^{\alpha\alpha} - RT \ln a_2^{\alpha\beta}] + RT (t_1^\alpha - t_2^\alpha) \ln \frac{a^\alpha a^{\alpha\beta}}{a^\beta} \quad (4)$$

Putting,

$$t_1^\alpha [\mu_1^{\alpha\beta} - RT \ln a_1^{\alpha\beta}] - t_2^\alpha [\mu_2^{\alpha\beta} - \mu_2^{\alpha\alpha} - RT \ln a_2^{\alpha\beta}] = -F(\Delta\phi)_{phases}^*$$

we have

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = -F(\Delta\phi)_{phases}^* + RT \left(\frac{U_1^\alpha - U_2^\alpha}{U_1^\alpha + U_2^\alpha} \right) \ln \frac{a^\alpha a^{\alpha\beta}}{a^\beta} \quad (5)$$

which can be rewritten as follows when a^α is taken to be unity,

$$(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = (\Delta\phi)_{phases}^* + \frac{RT}{F} \left(\frac{U_1^\alpha - U_2^\alpha}{U_1^\alpha + U_2^\alpha} \right) \ln \frac{a^\beta}{a^{\alpha\beta}} \quad (6)$$

The quantity $(\Delta\phi)_{phases}^*$ is difficult to measure or estimate theoretically. However, when $t \rightarrow \infty$, this is equal to phase potential, so that when $t \rightarrow \infty$, $a^\beta \rightarrow a^{\alpha\beta}$ and

$$(\Delta\phi)_{t \rightarrow \infty}^{\alpha,\beta} = (\Delta\phi)_{phases} \quad (7)$$

Again, to a first approximation for the non-equilibrium case,

$$d \ln \frac{a^\alpha}{a^\beta} = \left[\frac{H^\alpha - H^\beta}{RT^2} \right] dT \quad (8)$$

which can be written as

$$\ln \frac{a^\alpha}{a^\beta} = + \frac{(H^\alpha - H^\beta)}{RT_{av}^2} \Delta T$$

$$i.e., \ln \frac{a^\alpha}{a^\beta} - \ln \frac{a^{\alpha\beta}}{a^{\alpha\beta}} = + \frac{(H^\alpha - H^\beta)}{RT_{av}^2} (T_c - T_s) = - \frac{(H^\alpha - H^\beta)}{RT_{av}^2} \Delta T \quad (9)$$

where, $T_{av} = \frac{T_s + T_c}{2}$ and $a^{\beta\alpha\beta}$ denotes the activity of ions in saturated solution in non-equilibrium. Here, T_s = saturation temperature.

$\Delta T = T_s - T_c$, where T_c is the crystallization temperature. $\Delta H^{\alpha\beta} = H^\alpha - H^\beta$ is the net enthalpy change of the processes

Accordingly, we can write,

$$(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = (\Delta\phi)_{phases}^* + \frac{1}{F} \left(\frac{U_1^\alpha - U_2^\alpha}{U_1^\alpha + U_2^\alpha} \right) \frac{\Delta H^{\alpha\beta} \cdot \Delta T}{T_s} \quad (10)$$

The magnitudes of $(\Delta\phi)_{phases}$ and $(\Delta\phi)_{phases}^*$ are likely to be similar. Further, diffusion potential will have a negligible magnitude when measurement are made with the microelectrode.

Dissolution potential. We recall that dissolution process is a non-equilibrium process. During dissolution, the region of interest is again the liquid interface just adjacent to the solid. It should be noted that both solid and liquid regions

near the interface are in non-equilibrium so long as dissolution takes place. Bare ions get detached from the crystal lattice which jump into the liquid phase and get solvated at once. Amongst other factors, the sign and magnitude of the potential is supposed to depend on the relative speed of detachment of ions.

We consider the dissolution in a slightly under-saturated solution and that a certain amount of crystals adhere to the electrode when $t \rightarrow \infty$. We assume that diffusion potential is eliminated in the experiments. Following the treatment of Rastogi and Khan^{9*}, we get

$$-(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} + (\Delta\phi)^{\beta,\delta} = \frac{t_1^\alpha}{e_1} \Delta\mu_1^{\alpha\beta} + \frac{t_2^\alpha}{e_2} \Delta\mu_2^{\alpha\beta} + \frac{t_1^\beta}{e_1} \Delta\mu_1^{\beta\delta} + \frac{t_2^\beta}{e_2} \Delta\mu_2^{\beta\delta} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{where, } t_1^\alpha = \frac{U_1^\alpha}{U_1^\alpha + U_2^\alpha} \text{ and } t_2^\alpha = \frac{U_2^\alpha}{U_1^\alpha + U_2^\alpha} \quad (12)$$

and U_1^α and U_2^α are speeds of detachment of unhydrated (bare) cations and anions, respectively. Further, t_1 and t_2 are effective transport numbers of cation and anion at the β/δ interface^{9*}.

$$-(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = \left(\frac{t_1^\alpha}{e_1} \Delta\mu_1^{\alpha,\beta} + \frac{t_2^\alpha}{e_2} \Delta\mu_2^{\alpha,\beta} \right) \quad (13)$$

$$-(\Delta\phi)^{\beta,\delta} = \left(\frac{t_1^\beta}{e_1} \Delta\mu_1^{\beta,\delta} + \frac{t_2^\beta}{e_2} \Delta\mu_2^{\beta,\delta} \right) \quad (14)$$

Further,

$$(\Delta\phi)^{\beta,\delta} = - \frac{RT}{F} \left(\frac{U_1 - U_2}{U_1 + U_2} \right) \ln \frac{a^\beta}{a^\delta} \quad (15)$$

when we suppose that

$$\frac{a_1^\beta}{a_1^\alpha} = \frac{a_2^\beta}{a_2^\alpha} = \frac{a^\beta}{a^\alpha} \quad (16)$$

for uni-univalent electrolytes.

Equation (13) can be rewritten as

$$-(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = \frac{t_1^\alpha}{F} (\mu_1^\alpha - \mu_1^\beta) - \frac{t_2^\alpha}{F} (\mu_2^\alpha - \mu_2^\beta) \quad (17)$$

$$\text{where, } e_1 = -e_2 = F \quad (18)$$

The chemical potential in α and β phases are given by

$$\mu_i^\alpha = \mu_i^{\alpha\alpha} + RT \ln a_i^\alpha \quad (i=1, 2) \quad (19)$$

$$\mu_i^\beta = \mu_i^{\beta\beta} + RT \ln a_i^\beta \quad (i=1, 2) \quad (20)$$

* It was stated⁹ that the mobilities of the cations and anions at the crystal interface would be equivalent to ionic mobilities. This is a gross oversimplification. Further, there is a mistake of sign in equations (46) and (46) in the manuscript. Further, in equation (34), $(\Delta\phi)_{II} = -(\Delta\phi)_{diff}$ so that $(\Delta\phi)_{diff} = -RT/F \cdot (t_1 - t_2) \ln a^\beta/a$. Again, t_i may not necessarily be equal to conventional transport number since the transport across the interface β/δ has to be considered.

** The lower limit of second integral on the right hand side of equation (16) in Ref. 9 should be read as μ^β instead $\mu(\text{sat})$.

where, $\mu_i^{0\alpha}$ and $\mu_i^{0\beta}$ are the standard chemical potentials of species i in α - and β -phases, respectively. Hence, equation (17) can be written as

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = t_1^{\alpha}[\mu_1^{0\alpha} - \mu_1^{0\beta} - RT \ln a_1^{\alpha t}] - t_2^{\alpha}[\mu_2^{0\alpha} - \mu_2^{0\beta} - RT \ln a_2^{\alpha t}] - t_1^{\beta} \ln \frac{a_1^{\alpha} \cdot a_1^{\beta t}}{a_1^{\beta}} - t_2^{\beta} \ln \frac{a_2^{\alpha} \cdot a_2^{\beta t}}{a_2^{\beta}} \quad (21)$$

where, $a_1^{\alpha t}$ and $a_2^{\alpha t}$ denote the activities of ions 1 and 2 in the saturated solution. If $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}$ denotes the phase potential, it can be easily shown that

$$\mu_1^{0\alpha} - \mu_1^{0\beta t} - RT \ln a_1^{\alpha t} = -F(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}} \quad (22)$$

$$\mu_1^{0\alpha} - \mu_2^{0\beta t} - RT \ln a_2^{\alpha t} = +F(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}} \quad (23)$$

where, $\mu_1^{0\beta t}$ and $\mu_2^{0\beta t}$ are the corresponding standard chemical potentials in saturated solution. Thus $\mu_1^{0\beta}$ and $\mu_2^{0\beta}$ need not be equal. Hence, using equations (22), and (23) we get,

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = -F(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^* - RT(t_1^{\alpha} - t_2^{\alpha}) \ln \frac{a^{\beta}}{a^{\alpha t} a^{\alpha}} \quad (24)$$

where, $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^*$ may be called as non-equilibrium phase potentials which would be equal to $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}$ in equilibrium.

In writing equation (24) we have supposed that

$$\frac{a_1^{\alpha t} a_1^{\alpha}}{a_1^{\beta}} = \frac{a_2^{\alpha t} a_2^{\alpha}}{a_2^{\beta}} = \frac{a^{\alpha t} a^{\alpha}}{a^{\beta}}$$

Thus, equation (24) can be written as

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = -F(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^* - \frac{RT}{F} \left(\frac{U_1^{\alpha} - U_2^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}} \right) \ln \frac{a^{\beta}}{a^{\alpha} \cdot a^{\alpha t}} \quad (25)$$

Assuming that $a^{\alpha} = 1$ for solid, we have,

$$(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = (\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^* + \frac{RT}{F} \left(\frac{U_1^{\alpha} - U_2^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}} \right) \ln \frac{a^{\beta}}{a^{\alpha t}} \quad (26)$$

when $t \rightarrow \infty$ and solid still adheres to the electrode, $a^{\alpha} = a^{\alpha t}$ and $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^* = (\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}$.

Comparison of equations (6) and (26) shows that since $(\Delta\phi)^*$ would have the same value at a fixed temperature for both the cases, $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{diss}}$ and $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{ppt}}$ will have the same sign and their ratio (θ) at a fixed temperature would be given by,

$$\frac{(\Delta\phi)_{\text{diss}}}{(\Delta\phi)_{\text{ppt}}} \approx 1 \quad (27)$$

since

$$\frac{U_1^{\alpha} - U_2^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}} \approx \frac{U_1^{\beta} - U_2^{\beta}}{U_1^{\beta} + U_2^{\beta}}$$

if it is assumed that

$$U_i^{\alpha} \propto \frac{1}{r_i} ; U_i^{\beta} \propto \frac{1}{r_i}$$

Thermodynamic theory of freezing and melting potential: The freezing and melting potentials have been conceptually defined as follows. 'The freezing potential is the potential difference arising

from an electrical double layer developed at the in/solution interface by the ion-migration from the liquid phase. The algebraic sign of the freezing potential is the same as the electrostatic polarity (+) or (-), of the end of the dipolar double layer on the lattice side of the interface'. Similarly, the 'melting potential is the potential difference arising from an electrical double layer developed at a liquid/crystal interface by the process of melting (ion-migration) into the liquid phase. The algebraic sign of the melting potential is the same as the electrostatic polarity (+) or (-), of the end of the dipolar double layer on the lattice side of the interface'.

Both freezing and melting processes are non-equilibrium processes. Just at the solid/liquid interface, both phases are in non-equilibrium. This interface contains bare hydronium and hydroxyl ions which get attached to the crystal lattice during freezing. Similarly, when ions get detached from the lattice along with free H_2O molecule and clusters of hydrogen bonded H_2O molecules but only the ions contribute to the generation of electric potential. At the melting interface, there is a layer of free unhydrated ions.

We assume that H_3O^+ and OH^- are dissolved in a large mass of H_2O molecules. We denote the solid phase by α , non-equilibrium solid/liquid interface by β and bulk liquid phase by δ .

Following the procedure of Rastogi and Khan, we get the expression for the freezing potential $(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta}$,

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = t_1^{\alpha}[\mu_1^{0\alpha} + RT \ln a_1^{\alpha} - \mu_1^{0\beta} - RT \ln a_1^{\beta}] - t_2^{\alpha}[\mu_2^{0\alpha} + RT \ln a_2^{\alpha} - \mu_2^{0\beta} - RT \ln a_2^{\beta}] \quad (28)$$

where, F = Faraday, $(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta}$ = potential difference between α and β phases and $\mu_1^{0\alpha}$ and $\mu_2^{0\beta}$ are the standard chemical potential of i th species in α and β phases, respectively. Further t_1^{α} and t_2^{α} are the transport number of attachment of hydronium and hydroxyl ion to growing ice lattice which can be expressed as

$$t_1^{\alpha} = \frac{U_1^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}} ; t_2^{\alpha} = \frac{U_2^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}} \quad (29)$$

Equation (1) can be written as

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = t_1^{\alpha}[\mu_1^{0\alpha} - \mu_1^{0\beta} - t_2^{\alpha}[\mu_2^{0\alpha} - \mu_2^{0\beta}]] + (t_1^{\alpha} - t_2^{\alpha}) RT \ln \frac{a^{\alpha}}{a^{\beta}} \quad (30)$$

where, it is assumed as

$$\frac{a_1^{\alpha}}{a_1^{\beta}} = \frac{a_2^{\alpha}}{a_2^{\beta}} = \frac{a^{\alpha}}{a^{\beta}}$$

Equation (30) can be rearranged as

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = t_1^{\alpha}[\mu_1^{0\alpha} - \mu_1^{0\beta} - RT \ln a_1^{\beta}] - t_2^{\alpha}[\mu_2^{0\alpha} - \mu_2^{0\beta} - RT \ln a_2^{\beta}] + RT(t_1^{\alpha} - t_2^{\alpha}) \ln \frac{a^{\alpha} \cdot a^{\delta}}{a^{\beta}} \quad (31)$$

where, a^{δ} represents the normal liquid phase where the ions are hydrated.

We can write from equation (31),

$$-t_1^{\alpha}[\mu_1^{\alpha} - \mu_1^{\beta} - RT \ln a_1^{\alpha}] - t_2^{\alpha}[\mu_2^{\alpha} - \mu_2^{\beta} - RT \ln a_2^{\alpha}] = -(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^* \quad (32)$$

Since,

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} - F(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^* + RT \left(\frac{U_1^{\alpha} - U_2^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}} \right) \ln \frac{a^{\beta}}{a^{\alpha}} \quad (33)$$

where, we have assumed that a^{α} is the unity and $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^*$ is the non-equilibrium phase potential which is difficult to measure or estimate theoretically.

Further, equation (33) can be written as

$$(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = (\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^* + \frac{RT}{F} \left(\frac{U_1^{\alpha} - U_2^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}} \right) \ln \frac{a^{\beta}}{a^{\alpha}} \quad (34)$$

where $t \rightarrow \infty$, $a^{\beta} \rightarrow a^{\delta}$ and $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^{\alpha,\beta} = (\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}$.

We can write from equation (34),

$$(\Delta\phi)_{\text{freez}} = \frac{RT}{F} \left(\frac{U_1^{\alpha} - U_2^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}} \right) \ln \frac{a^{\beta}}{a^{\alpha}} \quad (35)$$

where, $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{freez}}$ represents the freezing potential.

We can derive an analogous equation for melting potential in the following manner. Using the procedure of Rastogi and Khan, we obtain the expression,

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = \frac{t_1^{\alpha}}{e_1} (\Delta\mu_1^{\alpha,\beta}) + \frac{t_2^{\alpha}}{e_2} (\Delta\mu_2^{\alpha,\beta}) \quad (36)$$

where, t_1^{α} and t_2^{α} are the transport number of detachment of hydronium and hydroxyl ions. This can be expressed as

$$t_1^{\alpha} = \frac{U_1^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}}; \quad t_2^{\alpha} = \frac{U_2^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}}$$

where, U_1^{α} and U_2^{α} are respectively the speed of detachment of hydronium and hydroxyl ions. Equation (37) can be rearranged as

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = \frac{t_1^{\alpha}}{e_1} (\mu_1^{\alpha} - \mu_1^{\beta}) - \frac{t_2^{\alpha}}{e_2} (\mu_2^{\alpha} - \mu_2^{\beta}) \quad (37)$$

where, $e_1 = -e_2$ and μ_1^{α} and μ_2^{β} are the chemical potential in α - and β -phases, respectively. The chemical potential of i th species in α - and β -phases can be given by equations (38),

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_i^{\alpha} &= \mu_i^{\alpha} + RT \ln a_i^{\alpha} \quad (i=1, 2) \\ \mu_i^{\beta} &= \mu_i^{\beta} + RT \ln a_i^{\beta} \quad (i=1, 2) \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

where, μ_1^{α} and μ_2^{β} are the chemical potential of species i in α - and β -phases, respectively. Hence equation (38) can be written as

$$-F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} = t_1^{\alpha}[\mu_1^{\alpha} + RT \ln a_1^{\alpha} - \mu_1^{\beta} - RT \ln a_1^{\beta}] - t_2^{\alpha}[\mu_2^{\alpha} + RT \ln a_2^{\alpha} - \mu_2^{\beta} - RT \ln a_2^{\beta}]$$

or,

$$\begin{aligned} -F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} &= t_1^{\alpha}[\mu_1^{\alpha} - \mu_1^{\beta} - RT \ln a_1^{\beta}] \\ &- t_2^{\alpha}[\mu_2^{\alpha} - \mu_2^{\beta} - RT \ln a_2^{\beta}] - (t_1^{\alpha} - t_2^{\alpha}) RT \ln \frac{a^{\alpha} a^{\delta}}{a^{\beta}} \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

where it is assumed that

$$\frac{a_1^{\alpha} \cdot a_1^{\delta}}{a_1^{\beta}} = \frac{a_2^{\alpha} \cdot a_2^{\delta}}{a_2^{\beta}} = \frac{a^{\alpha} \cdot a^{\delta}}{a^{\beta}}$$

where δ represents the bulk of solution and a_i^{α} is assumed to be unity, a_i^{δ} is the activity of i th species in bulk of solution.

We can write from equation (39),

$$-F(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}} = \mu_1^{\alpha} - \mu_1^{\delta} - RT \ln a_1^{\delta} \quad (40)$$

$$+ F(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}} = \mu_2^{\alpha} - \mu_2^{\delta} - RT \ln a_2^{\delta} \quad (41)$$

where, μ_i^{δ} is the corresponding standard chemical potential in liquid phase when the ions are hydrated. It should be noted that μ_i^{α} need not be equal to μ_i^{δ} . Using equations (39), (40) and (41), it can be easily shown that

$$\begin{aligned} -F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} &= -F(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^* - RT(t_1^{\alpha} - t_2^{\alpha}) \\ \ln \frac{a^{\beta}}{a^{\alpha} a^{\delta}} & \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

where, $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^*$ may be called as non-equilibrium phase potential which would be equal to $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}$ at equilibrium.

Equation (42) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} -F(\Delta\phi)^{\alpha,\beta} &= -F(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^* \\ -RT \left(\frac{U_1^{\alpha} - U_2^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}} \right) \ln \frac{a^{\beta}}{a^{\alpha}} & \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

where, a^{α} is assumed unity and when $t \rightarrow \infty$, $a^{\beta} \rightarrow a^{\delta}$ and $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}^* = (\Delta\phi)_{\text{phase}}$.

From equation (43) we can get,

$$(\Delta\phi)_{\text{melt}} = \frac{RT}{F} \left(\frac{U_1^{\alpha} - U_2^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}} \right) \ln \frac{a^{\beta}}{a^{\delta}} \quad (44)$$

where, $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{melt}}$ represents the maximum value of melting potential.

On comparison of equations (35) and (44), we find that provided the activity of α -phase remains unchanged during freezing and melting, the freezing and melting potential would be related by the expression,

$$(\Delta\phi)_{\text{melt}} / (\Delta\phi)_{\text{freez}} = \left(\frac{U_1^{\alpha} - U_2^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}} \right) / \left(\frac{U_1^{\alpha} - U_2^{\alpha}}{U_1^{\alpha} + U_2^{\alpha}} \right) \cdot \frac{T_m}{T_f} \quad (45)$$

Results

The data on precipitation potential using micro-electrode and dissolution potential using rotating electrode have been recorded in Table 1. The comparison between experimental and the theoretical values of precipitation potential has been made in Table 2. Similarly, the comparison between experimental and theoretical values of dissolution potential has been made in Table 3. The experimental results on freezing potential and melting potential have been recorded in Table 4.

TABLE 1—PRECIPITATION POTENTIAL USING (MICRO-ELECTRODE) AND DISSOLUTION POTENTIAL USING (ROTATING-ELECTRODE) OF ELECTROLYTES

Electrolyte	Precipitation potential* mV	Dissolution potential** mV	$\frac{(\Delta\phi)_{diss}}{(\Delta\phi)_{ppt}}$	θ
NaCl	-33 ± 2 (-54)	-22	0.67	0.9742
KCl	-44 ± 1 (-56)	-25	0.57	0.9742
KI	-48	-35	0.73	0.9742
KBr	-37 ± 3	-31	0.84	0.9742
BeSO ₄ .4H ₂ O	50 ± 1	38	0.76	0.9742
BeCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	—	-37*	—	—
CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O	31 ± 4	20	0.65	0.9742
Cu ₂ Cl ₂	—	-152*	—	—
NiSO ₄ .6H ₂ O	—	43	—	—
NiSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	—	44	—	—
(O ₂ H ₄) ₄ NI	-30 ± 2	23	0.77	0.9742
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	-71 ± 3	-124	1.74	0.9742
BaCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	—	-218	—	—
NH ₄ Cl	—	-161	—	—

* $\Delta T=12^\circ$, $T_0=323$ K figure in parenthesis denotes values obtained with large platinum electrode.

** $T=303$ K. * Ref. 5.

Discussion

The values of $\theta = T_d/T_p \frac{(\Delta\phi)_{diss}}{(\Delta\phi)_{ppt}}$ calculated using equation (27) have been compared in Table 1. The agreement is satisfactory as can be expected. The case of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ is a little anomalous, but, since in the precipitation process four K^+ along with one $Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$ have to get attached to the crystal lattice, $(U_1^a - U_2^a)$ is expected to be much smaller than $(U_1^d - U_2^d)$ since the detachment of four K^+ from the lattice would be easier process.

Exact experimental tests of equations (6) and (10) is difficult. However, these can be used to

compute approximate values of precipitation potentials. This can be done provided the values of a^{sat} and a^β ; ΔH ; and U_1^a and U_2^a are known. For NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI, values of (a^{sat}) are available. (a^β) for the unhydrated ions can be estimated from the following relation between activity coefficient f_\pm and an assumed concentration C ,

$$\log f_\pm = -\frac{a_0 \sqrt{C}}{1 + \beta a_0 \sqrt{C}} \quad (46)$$

and

$$a_\pm = f_\pm \cdot C$$

where, a_0 denotes the ion size parameter for bare ion. Similarly, ΔH can be estimated from crystal energy. Values of U_1^a and U_2^a are not known. However, we may suppose that

$$U_1^a = \frac{k_1}{r_1} \text{ and } U_2^a = \frac{k_2}{r_2} \quad (47)$$

since the speed of attachment of ions is likely to be inversely proportional to ionic radii. For sake of simplicity we put, $k_1 = k_2$, thus,

$$\frac{U_1^a - U_2^a}{U_1^a + U_2^a} \approx \frac{r_2 - r_1}{r_1 + r_2} \quad (48)$$

Substituting the values of the quantities a^{sat} , a^β , ΔH and $(U_1^a - U_2^a)/(U_1^a + U_2^a)$ obtained in the above manner in equations (10) and (6), values of $(\Delta\phi)_{ppt}$ have been computed for NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI. These are compared in Table 2 with the experimental values. The agreement is fair considering the uncertainties involved.

Equation (26) can also be examined in a similar manner. U_1^d and U_2^d would be inversely proportional to ionic radii of the bare ions so that an equation

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL VALUES OF PRECIPITATION POTENTIAL COMPUTED BY EQUATIONS (6) AND (10)

Electrolyte	r_2 Å	r_1 Å	f_\pm^{sat}	a^{sat}	$\log(a^\beta)^*$	ΔH kcal mol ⁻¹	T_0 K	$(\Delta\phi)_{ppt}^*$ mV	$(\Delta\phi)_{ppt}^\dagger$ mV	$(\Delta\phi)_{ppt}$ (exp.) mV
NaCl	1.81	0.95	0.986	7.179	0.428	-181	323	-9	-92	-33 ± 2
KCl	1.81	1.33	0.590	3.369	0.357	-163	323	-4	-40	-44 ± 1
KBr	1.95	1.33	0.636	4.034	0.447	-160	323	-2	-49	-37 ± 3
KI	2.16	1.33	0.683	6.368	0.619	-151	323	-4	-77	-48

* The values of a^β calculated from equation (46).
from equation (10).

** $(\Delta\phi)_{ppt}$ calculated from equation (6).

† $(\Delta\phi)_{ppt}$ calculated

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL VALUES (COMPUTED BY EQUATION (26)) OF DISSOLUTION POTENTIAL OF ELECTROLYTES

Electrolyte	$\log f$	$\log(a^\beta)^\dagger$	f^{sat}	a^{sat}	h^+	h^-	$\frac{r_2 - r_1}{r_2 + r_1}$	$\frac{r_2 h_1 - r_1 h_2}{r_2 h_1 + r_1 h_2}$	$\Delta\phi^*$ mV	$\Delta\phi^{**}$ mV	$\Delta\phi$ (exp.) mV
NaCl	-0.393	0.396	0.986	6.064	6	1	0.316	0.985	-7	-23	-22
KCl	-0.349	0.347	0.590	2.927	6	1	0.152	0.978	-1	-7	-25
KBr	-0.346	0.427	0.636	3.772	6	0	0.190	0.1	-2	-11	-31
KI	-0.346	0.640	0.683	6.270	6	0	0.315	1	-4	-13	-35

† Values of a^β calculated by equation (46).
calculated using values of equation (50).

* $(\Delta\phi)_{diss}$ calculated using values of equation (48).

** $(\Delta\phi)_{diss}$

TABLE 4—FREEZING AND MELTING POTENTIAL OF WATER CONTAINING IMPURITIES

Impurity	Concn.	$(\Delta\phi)_{\text{freez}}^a$	$(\Delta\phi)_{\text{melt}}^b$	θ^*
NaCl	2.5×10^{-6}	-183 ± 13	-210 ± 15 (-220 ± 18)	1.14
NaCl + Urea (10^{-4})	2.5×10^{-6}	-237 ± 10	-215 ± 17	0.91
NaCl + Sucrose (10^{-4})	2.5×10^{-6}	-59 ± 11	-2.8 ± 8	3.69
KCl	2.5×10^{-4}	-75 ± 7	-85 ± 7 (-92 ± 10)	1.08
KCl	2.5×10^{-4}	-250 ± 10	-245 ± 20	0.98
KCl + Urea (10^{-4})	2.5×10^{-4}	-275 ± 11	-259 ± 10	0.95
KCl + Sucrose (10^{-4})	2.5×10^{-4}	-88 ± 8	-240 ± 18	2.73
CaCl	2.5×10^{-4}	-125 ± 10	-160 ± 10	1.24
CaCl	2.5×10^{-4}	-225 ± 10	-290 ± 15	1.28
CaCl	2.5×10^{-6}	-200 ± 12	-225 ± 18	1.13
CaCl	2.5×10^{-6}	-125 ± 10	-150 ± 11	1.20
KI	2.5×10^{-4}	-285 ± 10	-300 ± 15	1.05
NH ₄ Cl	5×10^{-6}	218 ± 19	200 ± 12 (320 ± 15)	1.38
NH ₄ Cl + Urea (10^{-4})	5×10^{-6}	233 ± 13	315 ± 10 (325 ± 17)	1.12
NH ₄ Cl + Sucrose (10^{-4})	5×10^{-6}	88 ± 7	325 ± 10 (333 ± 12)	1.38
(NH ₄) ₂ CO ₃	5×10^{-6}	295 ± 13	$3^{\circ}0 \pm 17$ (335 ± 20)	1.18
(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ NI.H ₂ O	10^{-4}	-50 ± 5	-75 ± 7	1.5
Urea	1×10^{-4}	230 ± 12	-200 ± 18 (-220 ± 15)	-0.86

^a Measurements made with microelectrode. ^b Most of the measurements made with stationary electrode, however values of $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{melt}}$ in parenthesis in column 4 denotes, observed melting potential using rotating electrode.

identical to equation (48) can be used, viz.

$$U_1^a = \frac{k_1^1 h_1}{r_a}; U_2^a = \frac{k_2^1 h_2}{r_a} \quad (49)$$

since the speed of detachment would be more if ions have greater affinity for the solvent as measured by the hydration number. In equation (49), h_1 and h_2 represent the hydration number of cation and anion, respectively. If we again assume that $k_1^1 = k_2^1$,

$$\frac{U_1^a - U_2^a}{U_1^a + U_2^a} = \frac{r_a h_1 - r_1 h_2}{r_1 h_a + r_a h_1} \quad (50)$$

Thus, $(\Delta\phi)_{a, s}$ can be computed using equations (26) and (49) or (50). The values are reported in Table 3. Again the agreement is reasonably satisfactory considering the approximation involved in estimating the values of parameters. The agreement is better when equation (50) is used.

We can make a semi-quantitative comparison between theory and experiment at least in the case of freezing and melting potential of aqueous solution of alkali halides, NH₄Cl and (NH₄)₂CO₃. In these cases, ions segregating at the interface during freezing and melting would be the same. Therefore, U_1^a may be expected to be equal to U_1^a and $U_2^a = U_2^a$ so that

$$\left(\frac{U_1^a - U_2^a}{U_1^a + U_2^a}\right) \approx \left(\frac{U_1^a - U_2^a}{U_1^a + U_2^a}\right) \quad (51)$$

Using equations (45) and (51), we can obtain,

$$(\Delta\phi)_{\text{melt}}/(\Delta\phi)_{\text{freez}} = T_m/T_f \quad (52)$$

Since, $T_m > T_f$, it follows that

$$(\Delta\phi)_{\text{melt}}/(\Delta\phi)_{\text{freez}} > 1 \quad (53)$$

Experimental results recorded in Table 4 show that this expectation is in agreement with the experimental data.

The results on freezing and melting potentials of aqueous solution of urea are anomalous so far as the sign is concerned. In case of freezing, the speed of attachment of H₃O⁺ would be greater than OH⁻ in view of the chain mechanism, so that

$$U_1^a > U_2^a \quad (54)$$

hence, the sign of the freezing potential is positive. On the other hand, in case of melting since the size of OH⁻ is smaller than that of H₃O⁺,

$$U_2^a > U_1^a \quad (55)$$

hence, the sign of melting potential is negative. It should be noted that in both the cases, a^{β}/a^{α} is positive and greater than unity.

The influence of urea and sucrose on the magnitude of freezing potential of aqueous solution of electrolyte can also be explained on the basis of equation (34) and (44), where urea is added a^{β} would decrease while it would increase when sucrose is added. The values of a^{β} would be the same for the case of freezing and melting potential since the crystal/solution interface would be unaffected by the addition of urea or sucrose. Hence, the magnitudes of $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{freez}}$ would increase on the addition of urea and the same would decrease on the addition of sucrose as is experimentally observed.

The ratio of $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{melt}}/(\Delta\phi)_{\text{freez}}$ for aqueous solution of electrolyte and sucrose in a number of cases lies between 2 and 4. The anomaly seems to be due to the following reason.

During melting, the β -phase in the immediate vicinity of solid phase α has unhydrated ions in more or less a destructured environment, however, on freezing the β -phase would have such ions in a structured environment. Hence, the activity of H₂O in the two cases would be markedly different

and $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{moist}}$ would be much greater than $(\Delta\phi)_{\text{frees}}$.

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References

1. R. P. RASTOGI, R. K. DASS and B. P. DATRA, *Nature (London)*, 1961, **191**, 765.
2. R. P. RASTOGI and R. D. SHUKLA, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 1970, **41**, 2787.
3. R. P. RASTOGI, R. D. SHUKLA and S. BHAGAT, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1974, **121**, 1564.
4. R. P. RASTOGI, P. C. PANDEY and A. K. TRIPATHI, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, communicated.
5. R. P. RASTOGI and P. C. PANDEY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 449.
6. N. IBL, W. RICHARZ and H. WEDERKEHR, *Z. Phys Chem.*, 1975, **985**, 129.
7. H. L. GIRDHAR and R. P. MATTA, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1979, **89**, 407.
8. R. P. RASTOGI and S. A. KHAN, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1983, **130**, 1827.
9. R. P. RASTOGI and S. A. KHAN, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1980, **127**, 1989.
10. B. SCHARIFKER and G. HILLS, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1981, **130**, 81.
11. R. P. RASTOGI and A. K. TRIPATHI, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1995, **83**, 1404.
12. E. J. WORKMAN and S. E. REYNOLDS, *Phys. Rev.*, 1950, **78**, 254.
13. A. W. COBB and G. W. GROSS, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1969, **116**, 796.
14. H. R. PRUPPACHER, E. H. STEINBERGER and T. L. WANG, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 1968, **73**, 571.
15. J. M. CARANTI and A. J. ILLINGWORTH, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 1983, **88**, 8483.
16. V. LEFEBRE, *J. Colloid Interfac. Sci.*, 1983, **33**, 572.

ERRATA

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Page 48, line 32 : for $^3(\text{S}\cdots\text{O}_4)$ read $^3(\text{S}\cdots\text{O}_2)$

line 56 : for H. PIK, *J. Tetrahedron*

read H. J. PIK, *Tetrahedron*